

Risk Attitude Questionnaire USA

Thank you for considering participating in this research project. The purpose of this introduction is to explain to you what the study is about and what your participation would involve, to enable you to make an informed choice. The purpose of this study is to assess attitudes towards wind energy and the possibility of community ownership of onshore wind farms. This part of the study is an online survey to assess your attitude to financial risks. The online survey should take less than 6 minutes.

Participation in this study is completely voluntary. There is no obligation to participate, and should you choose to do so, you can refuse to answer specific questions, or decide to withdraw from the survey entirely. You maintain the right to withdraw from the study at any stage up to the point of data submission. At this point, your data will be collated with that of other participants and can no longer be retracted.

The information you give on the survey is stored on a University College Cork supported cloud storage platform, namely the Wind Value Microsoft Forms Account which may only be accessed from the researchers' UCC login. The data will be stored for minimum of ten years. The anonymized information you provide may contribute to research publications and/or conference presentations as well as a PhD thesis and research reports available on the project website at <https://windvalue.ie/>.

We do not anticipate any negative outcomes from participating in this study. Should you experience distress arising from the interview, the contact details for support services provided below may be of assistance.

This study has obtained ethical approval from the UCC Social Research Ethics Committee. If you have any queries about this research, you can contact me at peter.deeney@ucc.ie.

If you agree to take part in this study, please select the consent option below.

1. Consent.

The purpose and nature of the study has been explained to me in writing.

I am participating voluntarily. I am 18 or more years old.

I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether before it starts or while I am participating.

I understand that anonymity will be ensured in the write-up by disguising my identity.

I understand that disguised extracts from my interview and online survey (e.g. my name / location won't be used) may be quoted in presentations and publications (e.g. article, book chapter, student thesis, social media publicity of the study's findings, etc.), if I give permission below (please tick one box):

*

Yes, I agree to participate in this study

No, I do not agree to participate in this study

Please choose the option for which you have a preference from the following scenarios.

2. You have the opportunity to participate in a lottery in which you have an equal chance (50%) of winning \$100 or winning nothing. There is no fee to take part.

Option A: you participate in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Which option do you choose? *

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

3. You can choose between two investments:

Option A: offers an equal chance (50%) to gain \$5 or \$15

OR

Option B: offers you a certain gain of \$10.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

4. Suppose you have been fined and you have the opportunity to choose between two alternatives.

Option A: pay a fine of \$10

OR

Option B: have an equal chance (50%) of paying either \$5 or \$15.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

5. You may decide to participate to a lottery in which you have an equal chance (50%) to gain or lose \$5000.

Option A: you will take part in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

6. You may decide to take part in a lottery in which you have the an equal chance (50%) to gain or lose \$5.

Option A: you will take part in the lottery

OR

Option B: you do not participate.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

In the following scenarios you are faced with a choice of two options
Choose the option for which you have a preference

7. Option A: you have an equal chance (50%) of winning or losing \$5000

OR

Option B: you have an equal chance (50%) of winning or losing \$5.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

8. Option A: you have an equal chance (50%) of winning either \$5000 or \$15,000

OR

Option B: you a sure gain of \$10,000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

9. Option A: pay a fine of \$10,000

OR

Option B: have an equal chance (50%) of paying either \$5000 or \$15,000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

10. Option A: you have one chance in a million to win one million dollars

OR

Option B: gain \$1 for sure.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

11. Option A: You have a one in one thousand chance (0.1%) of losing \$1000, otherwise you lose nothing (zero)

OR

Option B: pay \$1 for sure.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

12. Option A: You have a one in 100 chance (1%) of winning \$10,000 and 99 in 100 (99%) of losing \$100

OR

Option B: An equal chance (50%) of winning \$1000 or losing \$1000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

13. Option A: 1% chance to lose \$10,000 and 99% chance to win \$101

OR

Option B: equal chance (50%) to win \$1000 or lose \$1000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

14. Option A: You have an equal chance (33%) to gain, \$0 or \$5000 or \$10,000

OR

Option B: You have an equal chance (25%) to gain, \$0 or \$2100 or \$7900 or \$10,000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

15. Option A: You have an Equal chance (33%) of, \$0 or \$5000 or -\$5000 (negative number means losing)

OR

Option B: You have an Equal chance (25%) of, \$2900 or \$5000 or -\$2900 or -\$5000.

Which option do you choose?

- Option A
- Option B
- Skip to Next Question

Socio-Demographic Questions

16. How do you see yourself: are you in general a person who takes risk or do you try to evade risk? Please self-grade your choice between 0 (I do not take risk at all) to 10 (I love to take risks).

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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17. If you were to consider investing in a windfarm project, what is the minimum rate of return you would expect to receive on your investment annually?

- 0%-5%
- 5%-10%
- More than 10%
- The return on investment is irrelevant, I would not invest in a wind farm project.
- Skip to Next Question

18. If you were to consider investing in a windfarm project with an attractive rate of return, what is the maximum amount you would be willing to invest?

- \$1-\$20,000
- \$20,000-\$50,000
- More than \$50,000
- Nothing, I would not invest in a wind farm project
- Skip to Next Question

19. Approximately, what is the distance from your home to the nearest wind turbine?

- Less than 1 mile
- 1 mile-3 miles
- 3 miles-6 miles
- More than 6 miles
- Skip to Next Question

20. What is the main deciding factor in your choice of electricity provider?

- Price
- Renewable Energy
- Combination of Price and Renewable Energy
- Skip to Next Question
- Other

21. Given your knowledge about the benefits of using wind energy, how likely are you to consider investing in a wind farm project?

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Neither likely nor unlikely
- Somewhat unlikely
- Very unlikely

22. What option below do you believe most accurately describes the purpose of wind farms?

- Profitable Business
- Climate Change Solution
- Electricity Generation
- Skip to next question

23. Are you aware of the EU Targets for Reducing Emissions by 2030?

- Not Aware
- Somewhat Aware
- Very Aware
- Skip to Next Question.

24. What is your age?

- 18 - 24
- 25 - 34
- 35 - 44
- 45 - 54
- 55 - 64
- 65 - 74
- 75 +

25. What is your gender?

26. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Primary
- Secondary
- Post Secondary
- University or College

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